

On the Elastic Constants of Cubic Crystals

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The second and third order elastic constants of solids of cubic systems have been calculated by extending the equations obtained by Schofield by considering the harmonic solid like limit and are used in applications to both solids and liquids. The third order elastic constant C_{111} has been evaluated extending equations developed for liquids. In spite of the isotropic approximation inherent in liquid state theories, which is generally absent in solids, the results are found to be in fair agreement.

The temperature variation of elastic constants of Al and Ag have been presented. We finally give a method for the evaluation of the pressure derivatives of second order elastic constants of a variety of solids which are found to be in good agreement with experiment. An extremely important conclusion that the pressure derivative of the I_1 integral is zero, has also been found.

LENNARD-Jones and Devonshire¹ and Eyring and Ree² extended solid state equations to predict liquid state properties. Salsburg and Wood gave an exact equation of state obtained through correlated cell theory³ which is an extension of the solid state concept. The molecular dynamic study of hard spheres by Alder and Wainright does not show any transition of solids to liquids but only shows a transition to gases⁴ which primarily reveals that in condensed systems the interplay of inter-molecular forces is the same. The molecular dynamic studies of Rahman⁵ of velocity auto-correlation function show a negative value meaning that the particle undergoes a vibratory motion. This is now known as caging effect. Thus in solids, particles are tied permanently to their equilibrium positions while in liquids, they do remain for some time showing their similarity. Several studies of amorphous solids and liquids show the same type of interference functions and radial distribution function⁶⁻¹⁰. Hence, even with the crude assumption of the existence of Cauchy's relationship which is true in liquids, it is still worthwhile to see how these extended equations apply to solids.

Theory and Results

Thus it is tempting to apply some of the equations derived by Schofield from a consideration of microscopic fluctuation¹¹ obtained in the long wave limit. The elastic constants can be conveniently written in the Voigt notation in the following form,

$$C_{111} = \rho k_B T [3 + \frac{2}{5} I_1 + \frac{1}{5} I_2] \quad (1a)$$

$$C_{112} = \rho k_B T [1 - \frac{2}{15} I_1 + \frac{1}{15} I_2] \quad (1b)$$

$$C_{44} = \rho k_B T [1 + \frac{4}{15} I_1 + \frac{1}{15} I_2] \quad (1c)$$

where, k_B is the Boltzmann's constant and $\rho (= N/V)$ is the number density. The I_1 and I_2 integrals are

defined in terms of the radial distribution function $g(r)$ by the following equations,

$$I_1 = \frac{\rho}{2k_B T} \int g(r) r \frac{du(r)}{dr} dr \quad (2)$$

$$I_2 = \frac{\rho}{2k_B T} \int g(r) r^3 \frac{d^2u(r)}{dr^2} dr \quad (3)$$

where, the symbols have their usual connotation.

The hardsphere potential is chosen because it gives mathematically simple analytical equations and a hardsphere condensed system does not show as pointed out earlier a solid-liquid transition but a direct phase transition to gases⁴. It is also well known that the structure of condensed system is primarily determined by repulsive forces between particles and the main effect of attractive forces between particles is to provide a uniform background potential¹² and the input data required is just the hardsphere diameter.

Hence, from the discussion above we believe that the use of equations (1) to determine the elastic constants with hardsphere potential will certainly be informative and useful.

Using the Dirac delta function properties, we get for I_1 as

$$I_1 = -2\pi\rho g(\sigma)\sigma^3 \quad (4)$$

where, σ is the hardsphere diameter and $g(\sigma)$ is the value of $g(r)$ at $r = \sigma$.

The integral I_2 for hardsphere potential is divergent and hence is treated purely as an empirical parameter and is evaluated empirically as given below. However, Schofield¹¹ obtained

$$\frac{1}{S(0)} \leq \frac{5}{3} - \frac{2}{9} I_1 + \frac{1}{9} I_2 \quad (5)$$

Hence, one can deduce the value of I_2 from a knowledge of $S(0)$. For hardspheres it can be shown through the use of Percus-Yevick equation¹³,

$$S(0) = \frac{(1-\eta)^4}{(1+2\eta)^2} \quad (6)$$

It is also known that $S(0)$ is related to the isothermal compressibility through the equation¹⁴

$$S(0) = \rho k_B T \beta_T \quad (7)$$

where, η is called the packing fraction and is given by

$$\eta = \frac{\pi \rho \sigma^3}{6} \quad (8)$$

Thus, from equations (6) and (7) the value of η can be calculated from a knowledge of β_T , the isothermal compressibility. It is important to note that η and hence σ are being fitted with experimental compressibility which depends upon the nature of intermolecular forces¹⁵ and hence this procedure of selecting η takes care of the forces operating in the substance.

When once η is selected, the value of $g(\sigma)$ can be immediately calculated¹⁶ for hardspheres and it is given by

$$g(\sigma) = \frac{1 + \eta/2}{(1 - \eta)^2} \quad (9)$$

Then, it is possible to calculate I_1 from equation (4) and I_2 from equation (5) noting the fact that under equilibrium conditions we take the equality sign in equation (5). Thus, from equation (1), one can calculate the second order elastic (SOE) constants. The values so calculated are given in Table 1. Further, we also assume that

$$\frac{dC_{12}}{dp} = \frac{dC_{44}}{dp} \quad (10)$$

It may be pointed out that Krishnan and Roy¹⁷ assumed that $C_{12} = C_{44}$.

From an inspection of the results given in Table 1 we see that inspite of the assumptions it may be noted that for alkali halides the agreement between experiment and theory is fair. The agreement in the case of some metals is not bad. Tungsten which obeys the Cauchy's rule gives a good result. In the case of metals, the agreement is not expected to be good since we have not taken into consideration the contribution from the conduction electrons as discussed by Fuchs¹⁸ and De Launay¹⁹.

Here, it may be remembered that in the present computation only one parameter enters into calculation. The earlier method due to Born does not work for non-ionic substances²⁰ as it assume $C_{12} = C_{44}$, and hence it is necessary to introduce several parameters and corrections¹⁹. The present computation takes into consideration the microscopic property $g(\sigma)$ and is analytical in nature requiring only one observation.

Temperature variation of elastic constants : We use the equation (1), (4) and (5) to evaluate SOES as a function of temperature. The necessary compressibility and density data as a function of temperature are taken from literature¹⁵. Calculations have been made for two typical metals, namely Al and Ag. It is found that in the temperature range calculated the variation of the elastic constant is

TABLE 1—ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF CUBIC CRYSTALS

Temp. = 298 K					
Substance	ρ (A ⁰⁻³)	$n = \frac{\eta}{\rho \sigma^3}$	C_{11} Expt./ (Calcd.)	C_{12} Expt./ (Calcd.)	C_{44} Expt./ (Calcd.)
Nb	0.054 45	0.705 2	2.46 (2.82)	1.89 (1.02)	0.29 (0.90)
Ge	0.045 46	0.654 8	1.80 (1.13)	0.48 (0.42)	0.67 (0.90)
Si	0.050 20	0.667 0	1.66 (1.51)	0.64 (0.61)	0.80 (0.48)
GaAs	0.044 30	0.662 1	1.19 (1.22)	0.54 (0.45)	0.59 (0.39)
Potassium alum	0.002 22	0.740 0	0.25 (0.27)	0.10 (0.10)	0.94 (0.90)
Magnetite	0.018 50	0.740 0	2.73 (2.83)	1.06 (1.00)	0.97 (0.93)
W	0.063 20	0.680 0	5.26 (5.41)	2.05 (1.95)	1.61 (1.76)
Al	0.059 50	0.632 1	1.07 (1.09)	0.61 (0.46)	0.24 (0.34)
Ag	0.586 00	0.681 9	1.24 (2.17)	0.94 (0.86)	0.47 (0.69)
LiF	0.061 18	0.626 1	1.11 (1.03)	0.42 (0.33)	0.65 (0.63)
LiCl	0.029 38	0.618 5	0.61 (0.46)	0.23 (0.17)	0.27 (0.14)
LiBr	0.024 02	0.618 2	0.40 (0.36)	0.19 (0.14)	0.19 (0.11)
LiI	0.015 72	0.610 7	0.28 (0.22)	0.14 (0.08)	0.14 (0.67)
NaF	0.036 70	0.649 1	0.94 (0.84)	0.21 (0.31)	0.28 (0.27)
NaCl	0.022 31	0.626 4	0.49 (0.39)	0.12 (0.14)	0.13 (0.12)
NaBr	0.018 75	0.624 6	0.40 (0.31)	0.11 (0.12)	0.10 (0.10)
NaI	0.014 74	0.617 1	0.10 (0.22)	0.08 (0.09)	0.09 (0.07)
KCl	0.016 03	0.628 8	0.40 (0.29)	0.06 (0.10)	0.06 (0.09)
KBr	0.019 92	0.626 7	0.33 (0.35)	0.05 (0.09)	0.05 (0.07)
RbCl	0.014 00	0.017 9	0.36 (0.22)	0.06 (0.08)	0.05 (0.07)
RbBr	0.012 20	0.623 1	0.31 (0.20)	0.05 (0.07)	0.04 (0.04)
RbI	0.100 70	0.624 1	0.25 (0.17)	0.04 (0.06)	0.03 (0.05)
CsI	0.010 45	0.623 1	0.24 (0.17)	0.06 (0.07)	0.06 (0.05)

linear with temperature as is true in most cases²¹. We give in Fig. 1, the linear temperature variation of elastic constants for the metals Ag and Al.

Third order elastic constants : In this section we give a method of evaluation of third order elastic (TOE) constants from equations obtained from liquid state theories.

Starting from equation (7) one can show,

$$2 \rho_0 C \left(\frac{\delta c}{\delta p} \right)_T = \frac{4 (1 - \eta)^2 (2 + \eta) \eta}{S(0) (1 + 2\eta)^2} \quad (11)$$

Thurston and Brugger have shown that for cubic crystals²²,

$$C_{111} = - \left[5 + 2 \rho_0 C \left(\frac{\delta c}{\delta p} \right)_{p=0} \right] C_{11} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 1. Temperature variation of elastic constants of Ag and Al.

It was also shown by Thurston²² that the non-linearity parameter K_p is related to the other elastic constants by the equation,

$$K_p = 3 + \frac{C_{111}}{C_{11}} \quad (13)$$

where,

$$K_p = \left(\frac{1}{2}C_{111} + \frac{3}{2}C_{112} + 6C_{166} \right) / A \quad (14)$$

$$\text{and } A = C_{11} + C_{12} + 2C_{44}$$

Noting the fact that

$$\frac{1}{\beta_T} = B = \frac{1}{3}(C'_{11} + 2C'_{12}) \quad (15)$$

we get,

$$\left(\frac{dB}{dT} \right) = C_1 = \frac{1}{3}(C'_{11} + 2C'_{12}) \quad (16)$$

Assuming the Cauchy's relation we have

$$C'_{11} = C'_{12} + 2C'_{44} \quad (17)$$

and through Thurston-Brugger's equations^{22,23} we get

$$\frac{9}{5}C_1 = \frac{-1}{3} \beta_T (C_{111} + 2C_{112}) \quad (18)$$

We now straight away compute the TOE constants using the well-known Thurston-Brugger's equations^{22,23}.

The pressure variation of bulk modulus C_1 has been evaluated through Gruneisen relation or through the Debye equation^{21,24},

$$C_1 = 2\nu + \frac{5}{3} \quad (19)$$

where, ν is the Gruneisen's constant, and are taken from literature²⁵. The values of TOE constants evaluated by this method have been given in Table 2 and are compared with experiment²⁶ where available or with other theoretical calculations²⁷.

TABLE 2—THIRD ORDER ELASTIC CONSTANTS* OF CUBIC CRYSTALS

Substance	C ₁₁₁	C ₁₁₂	C ₁₂₂	C ₄₄₄	C ₁₄₄	C ₁₆₆
LiF	-13.20 (-13.53)	-2.58 (-2.62)	-0.95 (0.92)	-0.39 (0.95)	-3.06 (0.97)	-1.58 (-2.54)
LiCl	-5.66 (-6.37)	-0.80 (-0.91)	-0.86 (0.31)	-0.04 (0.36)	-0.87 (0.37)	-0.79 (-0.98)
LiBr	-4.53 (-5.98)	-0.74 (-0.97)	-0.76 (0.23)	0.09 (0.28)	-1.39 (0.29)	-0.63 (-0.70)
LiI	-2.72 (-4.10)	-0.38 (-0.47)	-0.38 (0.16)	-0.08 (0.20)	-0.39 (0.20)	-0.36 (-0.49)
NaF	-11.37 (-8.56)	-1.14 (-1.44)	-2.26 (0.66)	-0.70 (0.54)	-1.09 (0.76)	-1.75 (-1.46)
NaCl	-5.00 [-8.00]	-0.67 [-0.57]	-0.77 [0.28]	-0.15 [0.27]	-0.76 [0.26]	-0.68 [-0.61]
NaBr	-3.96 (-5.38)	-0.41 (-0.44)	-0.77 (0.14)	-0.21 (0.20)	-0.43 (0.20)	-0.58 (-0.47)
NaI	-2.76 (-4.78)	-0.33 (-0.30)	-0.48 (0.10)	-0.04 (0.14)	-0.36 (0.15)	-0.89 (-0.88)
KCl	-3.61 [-7.01]	-0.34 [-0.22]	-0.76 [-0.13]	-0.21 [0.12]	-0.37 [0.13]	-0.68 [-0.25]
KBr	-3.20 (-4.62)	-0.22 (-0.27)	-0.97 (-0.11)	-0.26 (0.13)	-0.20 (0.14)	-0.46 (-0.30)
RbCl	-2.77 (-4.62)	-0.35 (-0.26)	-0.45 (0.08)	-0.06 (0.01)	-0.46 (0.14)	-0.84 (-0.30)
RbI	-2.71 (-2.58)	-0.18 (-0.14)	-0.50 (-0.03)	-0.14 (0.09)	-0.20 (0.09)	-0.32 (-0.17)
CsI	-2.16 (-2.30)	-0.31 (-0.36)	-0.36 (-0.29)	-0.11 (-0.33)	-0.16 (-0.22)	-0.29 (-0.32)

* Values in units of $\times 10^{12}$ dyne cm^{-1} . () Other theoretical values. [] Experimental values.

Evaluation of the pressure derivatives of elastic constants: We further extend the present method in the evaluation of the pressure derivatives of elastic constants.

From equation (1) we get the pressure derivatives of C_{11} as

$$C_{11} = \frac{dC_{11}}{dp} = C_{11}\beta_T + \frac{\rho K_B T}{5} (2I'_1 + I'_2) \quad (20)$$

and similarly we get for

$$C'_{11} = \frac{dC_{12}}{dp} = C_{12}\beta_T + \frac{\rho K_B T}{15} (-2I'_1 + I'_2) \quad (21)$$

and for

$$C'_{44} = \frac{dC_{44}}{dp} = C_{44}\beta_T + \frac{\rho K_B T}{15} (4I'_1 + I'_2) \quad (22)$$

From equation (15) we have

$$C_1 = 1 + \frac{\rho K_B T}{45} (2I'_1 + 5I'_2) \quad (23)$$

Differentiating equation (5) as well as (7) with respect to pressure and using the definition of

$$C_1 = \frac{\delta}{\delta p} (1/\beta_T) \text{ we get,}$$

$$\frac{9\beta_T}{S(0)} (C_1 - 1) = -2I'_1 + I'_2 \quad (24)$$

and finally we obtain,

$$I'_2 = \frac{9(C_1 - 1)\beta_T}{S(0)} \quad (25)$$

and $I'_1 = 0$

Equations (24) and (25) are very important as they yield a method in the evaluation of the pressure derivatives of the elastic constants. It is interesting to note that the pressure derivative of the I_1 integral (equation 25) is zero under the present assumptions. This is an important result.

Discussion

While computing the pressure derivative, we evaluate the modulus of M_1 to conform to the usual practice (*vide* Huntington²⁸), defined as

$$\begin{aligned} M &= \frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + 2C_{12}) \text{ or} \\ &= \frac{1}{3}(C_{11} - C_{12}) \text{ or} \\ &= C_{44} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

instead of the pressure derivatives of C_{ij} . The values of the pressure derivatives so calculated through the use of the equations (20) to (22) are given in Table 3. The values so calculated for metals, salts and an alloy agree fairly well with literature in spite of the approximations made in the evaluation of SOE's and TOE's. The most important equation connecting the TOE's with the liquid state equation is (12), while equations (5) and (7) are connected with TOE's.

We find that the calculated results do not coincide with each other especially in the case of TOE's.

TABLE 3—PRESSURE DERIVATIVE OF SECOND ORDER ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF SOME SUBSTANCES

Material	Modulus	$(\delta \ln M/\delta P)_T \times 10^{-11} \left(\frac{\text{cm}^3}{\text{dyne}} \right)$	
		Present	Literature [40]
KCl	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + 2C_{12})$	2.90	2.61
	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} - C_{12})$	3.20	3.16
	C_{44}	3.21	-0.74
NaCl	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + 2C_{12})$	2.18	2.46
	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} - C_{12})$	2.80	2.59
	C_{44}	2.37	0.21
Cu	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + 2C_{12})$	0.39	0.41
	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} - C_{12})$	0.45	0.25
	C_{44}	0.43	0.31
Ag	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + 2C_{12})$	0.56	0.60
	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} - C_{12})$	0.65	0.42
	C_{44}	0.62	0.50
Au	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + 2C_{12})$	0.39	0.39
	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} - C_{12})$	0.42	0.30
	C_{44}	0.41	0.42
Al	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + 2C_{12})$	0.55	0.51
	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} - C_{12})$	0.51	0.38
CuZn	$\frac{1}{3}(C_{11} + C_{12})$	0.57	0.40
	C_{44}	0.57	0.32

Thus in the evaluation of the TOE's by Prasad and Suryanarayana²⁹ and that of Graham *et al.*³⁰ for columbium, differ even in sign for C_{144} . Similarly, the widely varying results obtained by various authors for Al and Ni in the evaluation of C_{111} *etc.* are well brought out in a review by Reddy and Kesavaraju³¹. We should also bear in mind the variation in the experimental results as well³¹.

From an inspection regarding the pressure variation of SOE's calculated by the present method, it appears to work very well considering the simplicity of the equations for a variety of solids except in the case of the pressure variation of C_{44} for the alkali halides. In this connection it is important to note that C_{44} from equation (22) does not yield a negative value. This appears to be the case when the substance is highly anisotropic. The anisotropic factor is usually defined as

$$S = \frac{2C_{44}}{C_{11} - C_{12}} \quad (27)$$

Thus, in the case of KCl, the anisotropic value is 0.37 far away from unity while in the case of NaCl it is 0.70. The results of $[\partial \ln C_{44}/\partial p]_T$ of these salts show the same trend. However, the S factor is less than unity in both the salts. When S is greater than unity the value of $[\partial \ln C_{44}/\partial p]_T$ is not affected much as is found to be the case in Cu, Ag and Au where the values of S are 3.21, 2.88 and 2.91, respectively. The pressure variation of $\{\partial \ln [C_{11} + 2C_{12}]/\partial p\}_T$ appears to be in satisfactory agreement with literature values. It must be remembered that the deviation of $[\partial \ln C_{44}/\partial p]_T = \frac{1}{C_{44}} \left[\frac{\partial C_{44}}{\partial p} \right]_T$ appears to be large because of the occurrence of C_{44} , a small quantity in the denominator. Further, the applicability of the present equation in the evaluation of the pressure derivatives of

$\left[\frac{\partial \ln M}{\partial p} \right]_{\tau}$ to a variety of solids and their satisfactory agreement with experiment appears to be due to the choice of the use of β_{τ} through $S(0)$ and $g(\sigma)$.

The present method appears to be the only method wherein the use of radial distribution function is made and hence forms a new method of approach in the evaluation of elastic constants.

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